

Effect of dielectric constant of urea-water medium on protonation constants of L-glutamic acid and L-methionine

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Abstract : An electrometric investigation of protonation equilibria of L-glutamic acid and L-methionine in aqua-urea media of varying composition (0–36.83% w/v) has been made at different concentrations of the amino acids at 303 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³. The best fit chemical models were arrived at based on firm statistical grounds employing crystallographic *R* factor, χ^2 , skewness and kurtosis. The variation in the protonation constants with the dielectric constant of the medium is attributed to the electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces and to protonating ability of urea.

Keywords : Complex equilibria, protonation, glutamic acid, methionine, urea.

L-Glutamic acid (Glu) and L-methionine (Met) are vital amino acids present in amino acid pools and in active site cavities of several enzymes^{1,2}. Glutamate is also a neurotransmitter at the synapse between the photoreceptors and bipolar cells of the vertebrate retina³. Glutamate receptors in the vertebrate central nervous system are classified depending on the antagonistic action of *N*-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA), kainate or quisqualate⁴. Blood plasma samples of HIV-1-infected persons contain elevated glutamic acid concentration up to 6-fold compared to normal levels⁵. All plants and some forms of bacteria can synthesise methionine from cobalamine⁶. Met acts as a methyl group donor in biological transmethylation processes in the form of S-adenosyl methionine (SAM)⁷.

Due to the biological significance of the title amino acids, understanding in their protonation-deprotonation equilibria in media of varying dielectric constant is of vital importance. Earlier, we studied the effect of *N,N'*-dimethyl formamide⁸, urea⁹ and sodium lauryl sulphate¹⁰ on the protonation equilibria of L-glutamic acid. Now, we report the protonation equilibria of L-glutamic acid and L-methionine in urea-water mixtures in this communication.

Results and discussion

The results of the best fit models that contain the type of species and overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. A very low standard deviation in log β values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (the sum of the squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, indicate that the experimental data can

be represented by the model. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals of many systems vary nearer to the normal distribution. Very few systems form a leptokurtic and others form platykurtic pattern. The values of skewness recorded in Table 1 are between -1.34 and 0.89. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution, hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic *R*-value recorded. These statistical parameters, thus show that the best fit models portray the acido-basic equilibria of L-glutamic acid and L-methionine in aqua-urea mixtures. The protonation equilibria for L-glutamic acid and L-methionine are given in Fig. 1.

Effect of dielectric constant :

The variation of protonation constant or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic. Born's classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant. Hence, the logarithm of protonation constant varied in such a manner that log K_1 and log K_3 values vary linearly whereas log K_2 passes through a maximum as the reciprocal of dielectric constant increases for glutamic acid as shown in Fig. 2. For methionine log K_2 value varies linearly but log K_1 value passes through maximum.

Fig. 1. Protonation equilibria of glutamic acid and methionine.

The deviation from the expected linear trend may be due to a combination of electrostatic (long range, non-specific or universal) and non-electrostatic solute-solvent interactions in binary urea-water mixtures. In the case of urea and formamide

the dielectric constant of the co-solvent is larger than that of water. Both electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects should be considered even in the case of simple acid-base equilibria¹¹.

Fig. 2. Variation of stepwise protonation constant ($\log K$) with reciprocal of dielectric constant ($1/D$) in urea-water mixtures : (A) glutamic acid, (\diamond) $\log K_1$, (\square) $\log K_2$, (\circ) $\log K_3$; (B) methionine, (\diamond) $\log K_1$, (\square) $\log K_2$.

Amino acids can exist in anionic, zwitterionic and cationic forms in different equilibria presently investigated as shown in Fig. 1. The cation stabilizing nature of co-solvents, specific solvent-water interactions, charge dispersion and specific interactions of co-solvent with solute indicated by the changes in the solubility of different species in aqua-organic mixtures account for the deviation of classical linear relationship of $\log K^M$ with $1/D$. The reason for this trend is two fold. Urea forms zwitterions which change the dielectric constant of the medium and also acts as a ligand and competes with the ligand for protons¹².

Urea acts as a denaturant of macromolecules. The denaturing effect of urea on proteins can occur in two ways : (1) direct interaction of urea molecules with amide and peptide groups, to destroy intermolecular hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions¹³ that are involved in the maintenance of ternary structures, and (2) urea molecules exhibit their influence through changes in water structure¹⁴. The increased solubilities of amino acids¹⁵ and hydrocarbons¹⁶ in presence of urea support the former mechanism. The negative heat capacities of transfer of certain amino acids¹⁷ from water to aqueous urea solution and increments in the critical micellar concentration¹⁸ of certain surfactants suggest that urea may reduce¹⁹ the co-operative structure of water.

Table 1. Best fit chemical models of acid-base equilibria of L-glutamic acid and L-methionine in urea-water mixtures
Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

w/v of urea	L-Glutamic acid									
	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	log β_3 (SD)	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	χ^2	R-factor	Kurtosis	pH-range
00.00	9.30 (1)	13.46 (1)	15.52 (1)	141	0.110	0.89	13.38	0.00438	6.84	1.74–10.0
05.80	9.02 (1)	13.00 (1)	14.96 (2)	91	0.219	-0.12	36.55	0.00789	4.71	2.00–9.10
11.52	8.78 (1)	12.54 (2)	13.88 (3)	99	0.278	0.01	8.38	0.00940	3.43	1.90–9.10
20.31	9.01 (4)	16.70 (6)	18.72 (7)	216	3.371	0.08	13.63	0.01687	3.62	1.40–10.0
29.64	8.49 (3)	15.60 (6)	17.21 (6)	246	2.133	-1.09	48.36	0.11189	9.64	1.30–9.50
36.83	8.39 (7)	13.20 (4)	14.89 (3)	287	10.723	0.34	105.78	0.21656	3.92	1.10–9.30
L-Methionine										
00.00	8.86 (1)	11.06 (7)	–	100	0.076	0.23	1.44	0.004592	3.62	1.80–9.20
05.80	8.57 (1)	10.64 (2)	–	69	0.433	0.14	4.72	0.014238	2.44	2.00–8.90
11.52	8.33 (1)	9.88 (2)	–	75	0.463	0.19	4.24	0.015404	2.41	1.90–9.00
20.31	8.51 (7)	15.95 (8)	–	79	8.270	-1.23	15.97	0.065791	4.02	2.00–9.60
29.64	8.11 (9)	14.80 (20)	–	76	17.920	-1.34	22.95	0.099069	3.63	2.00–9.20
36.83	7.96 (4)	9.33 (5)	–	207	4.841	0.49	11.08	0.020579	3.69	1.40–9.00

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP - m) \times 10^7$, where, m = number of species.

Distribution diagrams :

The distribution plots produced using the protonation constants from the best fit models show the formation of LH_3^+ , LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} in the case of L-glutamic acid and LH_2^+ , LH and L^- in the case of L-methionine (Fig. 3). In both the cases, the zwitterionic form (LH_2 in the case glutamic acid and LH for methionine) is present to an extent of 90% in the pH ranges 1.6–5.4 and 2.0–8.0, respectively. But the existence of this species is restricted to a narrow pH range as the urea content is increased due to destabilization of the zwitterion with increased dielectric constant of the medium.

Experimental

Solutions of L-glutamic acid (G.R., E. Merck, Germany) and L-methionine (Himedia, India) were prepared in triply-distilled water. Urea (E. Merck, India, 99.5% purity) was used. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA). The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method²⁰.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of urea, maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with NaNO_3 at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. This ionic strength assumes importance because the biofluids have an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³. In order to study the protonation constants under mimicked physiological

Fig. 3. Species distribution diagrams : (A) glutamic acid, (B) methionine.

conditions, the present study has been carried out at this ionic strength. Requisite amounts of water and urea were added such that the overall percentages of urea were in the range 0–36.83% w/v. The amounts of mineral acid and amino acids maintained were in the ranges of 1.00–3.12 mmol and 0.25–0.5 mmol, respectively, in different experiments to monitor hydrogen ion concentration. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. The pH meter was calibrated by using 0.05 mol dm⁻³ potassium hydrogen phthalate and 0.01 mol dm⁻³ borax solutions. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred urea-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. Titration of strong acid with alkali was carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. The calomel electrode was filled with urea-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand, to maintain identical dielectric constant on both the sides of the glass membrane. This also avoids the variation of liquid junction potential due to change in the solvent composition. Titrations with different ligand concentrations were carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ NaOH. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹².

Modeling strategy :

The approximate protonation constants of L-glutamic acid were calculated with the computer program SCPHD²¹. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program, MINQUAD75²², which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. The variation of stepwise protonation constants was analyzed on electrostatic grounds on the basis of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Conclusions :

- (i) L-Glutamic acid forms LH₃⁺ at low pH and deprotonates with the formation of LH₂, LH⁻ and L²⁻ successively with increase in pH.
- (ii) L-Methionine forms LH₂⁺ at low pH and deprotonates with the formation of LH and L⁻ with increase in pH.
- (iii) Urea acts as denaturant and structure breaker of water and increases the dielectric constant of the medium and thus it has an effect on the protonation constants of L-glutamic acid and L-methionine.

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